

THE EFFECT OF H-ION CONCENTRATION ON THE VISCOSITY CHANGES IN THORUM PHOSPHATE GEL-FORMING MIXTURES DURING SETTING

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The investigation deals with the measurement of changes in viscosity taking place during the setting of thorium phosphate gel-forming mixtures of different p_H . It has been found that the rate of change of viscosity with time increases when the p_H is reduced up to a certain value; further reduction in p_H causes a decrease. Two sets of straight lines are obtained when values of $\log (\eta/\eta_0)$ are plotted against t , one set corresponding to mixtures having p_H values ranging from the maximum to that of the mixture setting in minimum time and the other to those having lower p_H . The effect of the addition of increasing amounts of ethyl alcohol to mixtures having p_H greater and less than that of the mixture setting in minimum time has been found to be different and it is surmised that this behaviour indicates the difference in the structures.

Several workers have studied the changes in viscosity occurring in a gel-forming system during gelation. Most of the work of this nature on inorganic gel-forming system has been carried out by Prasad and co-workers (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1932, 36, 1384). In these studies very little systematic work has been done on the viscosity changes with time during the setting of gels having different H-ion concentrations. In the present investigation an attempt has been made to measure the viscosity changes during the setting of thorium phosphate gels from mixtures of different H-ion concentrations. Mehta, Parmar and Prasad (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 13, 128) have studied the effects of the addition of increasing amounts of hydrochloric, nitric and sulphuric acids on the viscosity changes during the setting of thorium phosphate gels and have found that such an addition of the first two acids increases the rate of change in viscosity with time, while with the third one, the rate at first decreases and then increases.

EXPERIMENTAL

Scarpa's method employed by Prasad and Modak (*Proc. Indian Acad. Sci.*, 1940, A 11, 282) was used in this investigation. The diameter and the length of the capillary tube were 0.0995 cm. and 4.395 cm. respectively, and the volume of the bulb between the two marks was 1.72 c.c. The pressure applied for suction was 20 cm. of water and was kept constant throughout. The constant of the apparatus was determined by using sucrose solution and was found to be 0.00218.

The concentrations of solutions of thorium nitrate, phosphoric acid and hydrochloric acid used were 6% ($N/2$), 2*N* and 2*N*, respectively. They were prepared in the same manner as described by Nathan (to be published in a later issue of this Journal).

The chosen constituents of the gel-forming mixture were taken in two separate test-tubes which were placed in the thermostat maintained at 35 ± 0.02 , till they acquired the temperature of the bath. They were then mixed in the manner described by Nathan (*loc. cit.*) and the mixture was poured in the viscosity bottle.

TABLE I.

$y=0.0$ c.c. $p_H=1.42$		$y=0.20$ c.c. $p_H=1.00$		$y=0.50$ c.c. $p_H=0.79$		$y=0.75$ c.c. $p_H=0.68$		$y=1.00$ c.c. $p_H=0.50$		$y=1.50$ c.c. $p_H=0.45$	
t	η	t	η	t	η	t	η	t	η	t	η
61.5 sec.	3.781	65 sec.	4.664	204 sec.	6.666	75 sec.	5.883	67 sec.	6.107	69 sec.	8.211
125	4.105	123	5.219	272	8.110	116	7.230	143	7.717	159	13.020
197	4.609	250	5.824	362	9.544	290	11.110	229	12.220	313	26.510
581	4.766	308	5.864	462	11.950	405	14.510	339	16.220	645	56.400
664	4.784	425	6.493	626	15.930	531	19.760	485	23.440		
726	5.055	532	7.701	783	20.900	707	28.020	735	40.370		
788	5.333	615	8.020	949	28.610	994	42.800	1620	108.900		
1267	6.610	732	9.990	1252	41.270	1402	71.650	3215	204.500		
1596	7.335	833	10.330	1617	63.980						
1883	7.985	965	12.110	2273	101.900						
2077	8.109	1087	13.450	3142	210.300						
2150	8.421	1212	15.220								
2478	9.210	1340	17.570								
		1517	20.380								
		1722	24.250								
		1987	30.200								
		2525	43.020								
$y=2.00$ c.c. $p_H=0.30$		$y=2.50$ c.c. $p_H=0.26$		$y=3.00$ c.c. $p_H=0.200$		$y=3.50$ c.c. $p_H=0.09$		$v=4.00$ c.c. $p_H=low$		$y=4.54$ c.c. $p_H=very\ low.$	
t	η	t	η	t	η	t	η	t	η	t	η
76 sec.	10.500	96 sec.	17.120	154 sec.	33.430	159 sec.	47.810	119 sec.	20.900	54 sec.	5.932
165	16.380	320	40.330	797	86.110	515	65.720	395	40.380	119	8.120
317	27.850			1350	157.000	1212	110.300	647	50.500	204	12.010
770	73.480							1019	58.000	342	13.450
1230	150.000							1472	68.560	587	14.200
								2045	83.000	765	14.200
								2857	100.900	877	14.540
										1018	14.630
										1175	14.900
										1332	15.050
										1463	15.050
										1662	15.200
										1767	15.200
										2182	15.500

Viscosity readings (expressed in millipoises) were taken after known intervals (t , expressed in minutes) from the time of mixing and the results obtained are given in Table I in which y represents c.c. of 2*N*-HCl added to the mixture. These results are shown in Fig. 1. The measurement of the viscosity in each case was continued until the mixture would not flow through the capillary tube of the viscometer.

FIG. 1.

DISCUSSION

Various viscosity-time curves in Fig. 1, though similar in shape, have different slopes. This shows that some gels have a tendency to set quicker than others.

It was observed that after a certain time some gel-forming mixtures had become so viscous that the measurement of viscosity was rendered impossible. This was particularly observed with mixtures containing 0.3 c.c. of phosphoric acid, and hence in this case, the viscosity changes for only a limited number of mixtures have been measured.

It will be observed that with an increase in the amount of HCl in the gel-forming mixture containing 0.2 c.c. of phosphoric acid, the rate of change of viscosity increases with an addition up to 3.0 c.c. of HCl, that is, with a decrease in p_H from 1.42 to 0.20. Further reduction in p_H , caused by further addition of HCl, causes a decrease in the rate of change of viscosity with time. The same has been found to be the case with gels prepared in presence of 0.3 c.c. of phosphoric acid, the change from the increase in the rate of change of viscosity with the progress of gelation to a decrease seems to take place with the mixture having p_H 0.75.

If we take as a basis of comparison the time taken by the gel to attain a certain viscosity and take this time as proportional to the time of setting of the gel, we can

follow the setting of these gels in the same manner as determined by the actual measurement of the time of setting. The time required to attain a viscosity of 70 millipoises was read from Fig. 1 in the case of all mixtures and these values have

FIG. 2.

FIG. 3.

been plotted against the c.c. of HCl present in the mixtures. The curve obtained is shown in curve I, Fig. 2 and the corresponding data are given in Table II.

TABLE II.

HCl.	Time.	HCl.	Time.
0.50 c.c.	1750 sec.	2.00 c.c.	750 sec.
0.75	1390	3.00	560
1.00	1250	3.50	600
1.50	690	4.00	1520

TABLE III.

HCl.	Viscosity.	HCl.	Viscosity.	HCl.	Viscosity
0.00 c.c.	5.0	1.00 c.c.	38.0	3.00 c.c.	86.0
0.20	8.0	1.50	56.0	3.50	80.0
0.50	18.0	2.00	64.0	4.00	52.0
0.75	28.0	2.50	...	4.50	15.0

It will be noted that the values for mixtures containing no HCl and for those containing 0.2 c.c. and 4.5 c.c. of the acid, have not been given in the above table, because in these cases the maximum value of viscosity, when the flow in the capillary tube could not be observed, took place after a long time and the shape of the curve was consequently very flat. It will be seen from the nature of the curve in Fig. 2, that it is not different from the curve obtained by plotting the time of setting of the mixture containing 5.0 c.c. of the thorium nitrate and 0.3 c.c. of phosphoric acid, against c.c. of 2N-HCl added to the mixture (*cf.* Nathan, *loc cit.*). There is the similar flat minimum which would be expected. These results are very interesting in showing that even before the formation of firm gel takes place, the nature of the changes brought about by the addition of HCl is similar.

Alternatively the same information regarding the effect of the addition of HCl to the same gel-forming mixture, as given above, could be obtained by noting the viscosities of the several gel-forming mixtures at a given interval of time after mixing. The applicability of these views in the present case has been shown by reading the values of viscosity from the various curves in Fig. 1, at an interval of 700 seconds from the time of mixing. The values thus obtained are given in Table III and shown graphically by curve II in Fig. 2. This time interval is selected because in most cases the viscosity-time curve is straight, and hence represents a certain amount of regularity of viscosity changes with time.

It will be observed from curve II, Fig 2 that the viscosity at first rises, reaches a maximum value and then falls. Also the maximum viscosity value corresponds roughly with the minimum time of attaining a definite viscosity. This conforms to the view that even when a gel does not set, the physicochemical changes taking place in it are of the same nature and it only requires a different method of examination to bring them out. This point is brought out even in a more striking manner in the following.

Nathan (*loc. cit.*) observed that the times of setting and even the minimum time of setting, for mixtures prepared from 0.2 c.c. of phosphoric acid and different amounts of HCl are too long. The volume of HCl which causes the mixture containing 0.20 c.c. of phosphoric acid to set in minimum time can be calculated from the relation, $y = 4 - 6x$, which has been found to hold with several mixtures. This value comes out to be 2.80 c.c. It will be seen from curves I and II in Fig. 2 that the volume of HCl corresponding to the minimum and maximum points in the curves is 3.0 c.c. The observed result is therefore in very good agreement with the calculated one. In other words this method can be employed to determine the conditions necessary for the setting of the gel in minimum time.

In order to determine the manner by which the viscosity of the gel-forming mixture changes with time, the value of the viscosity at zero time was obtained by extrapolating viscosity-time curves in Fig. 1, to zero time and the values of viscosity at definite intervals of time were read from the curves. The values of $\log(\eta - \eta_0)$ at different intervals of time (t) for different mixtures containing 0.2 c.c. of phosphoric acid were plotted against t and the curves obtained were found to be straight lines. This shows that the relation, $\eta - \eta_0 = ae^{kt}$ is obeyed. These results are in agreement with those obtained by previous authors (Mehta, Parmar and Prasad, *loc. cit.*). It is further noticed that the straight lines for all mixtures containing up to 3.0 c.c. of HCl form one bunch, while those with mixtures containing larger amounts of HCl form another. It will be remembered that 3.0 c.c. of HCl corresponds to the minimum time of setting. Hence it appears that two sets of lines are obtained when $\log(\eta - \eta_0)$ is plotted against t , one for the mixtures corresponding to the volumes of HCl smaller than that corresponding to the minimum time and the other for the greater amounts.

Prasad, Mehta and Desai (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1932, 36, 1384) have found that alcohol have an accelerating effect on the rate of increase of viscosity of silicic acid gel-forming mixtures in alkaline and moderately acidic media (only within a very small range of the alcohol added) and a retarding one in fairly acidic medium.

Mehta, Parmar and Prasad (*loc. cit.*) found that the addition of non-electrolytes to thorium phosphate gel-forming mixtures decreases the rate of change of viscosity. Prasad and Shejwalkar (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1940, 17, 508) and Prasad and Modak (*loc. cit.*) also found that the rate of change of viscosity with time of gel-forming mixtures studied by them, decreases with the addition of increasing amounts of alcohol.

In this study the effect of ethyl alcohol was examined on mixtures containing 0.20 c.c. of phosphoric acid and 0.5 and 4.0 c.c. of HCl. These two mixtures correspond to points before and after the minimum time of setting. Increasing amounts of ethyl alcohol were added to the mixtures in the same manner as described by Nathan (*loc. cit.*) and the results obtained were plotted graphically.

It is observed from the nature of these curves that the effect of the addition of increasing amounts of ethyl alcohol to the mixture containing 0.5 c.c. of HCl is different from that of the mixture containing 4.0 c.c. All the viscosity-time curves in the former case rise fairly steeply with their concavity towards the viscosity axis, while in the latter case the curves are fairly flat rising with their concavity towards the time axis. Further, with the addition of increasing amounts of alcohol the viscosity of the mixture, containing 0.5 c.c. of HCl at first decreases, reaches a minimum value; then it increases and reaches a maximum value and finally falls when the amount of alcohol in the mixture exceeds 0.70 c.c. On the other hand with similar addition of alcohol to mixture containing 4.0 c.c. of HCl, the viscosity at first increases, reaches a maximum value; it then falls and reaches a minimum value and then increases again. Only a limited amount of alcohol could be added to this mixture. The viscosity curves, when the amount of alcohol is increased beyond 0.40 c.c., have a tendency to slope downwards, probably due to the separation of the particles in the gel-forming mixture.

The above mentioned results have been brought out in Fig. 3 in which the curves I and II have been obtained on plotting the viscosity attained at 1800 seconds after mixing the gel-forming constituents against the c.c. of alcohol added to the two mixtures, containing 0.5 and 4.0 c.c. of HCl, respectively. The difference in the structure of the gels forming from mixtures having the time of setting lower and higher than the minimum time of setting is thus brought out from the effect of the addition of alcohol on the viscosity changes with time of these mixtures. It may be noted that these results are essentially different from those obtained by previous workers (Mehta, Parmar and Prasad, *loc. cit.*).

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